

STUDIES ON RANCIDITY OF BUTTERFAT. PART VIII CHEMICAL
ACCELERATORS OF RANCIDITY. THE EFFECT OF PEROXIDES
AND VOLATILE PRODUCTS OF OXIDATION OF FAT
ON RANCIDITY

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Addition of a very small amount of rancid fat greatly reduces the induction period of fresh fats, whilst products of oxidation of fats have no effect on the development of rancidity of fresh fat.

The interaction of oxygen with fats and oils provides curves typical for auto-catalytic reaction, characterised by a phase of slow change which precedes rapid oxidation; this period of slow oxidation has been described as the 'induction period' of the fat. This induction period is of greatest practical importance since it determines the length of time for which a product can be kept in storage without becoming rancid. The explanation usually advanced to account for this induction period is that some product or products of the reaction, most probably the peroxides, function as positive catalyst in promoting further oxidative changes, these substances being considered to accumulate in the fat until present in sufficient concentration to produce intense oxidation. Besides peroxides, it has also been questioned whether the volatile products of oxidation can act as accelerators in the development of rancidity by autoxidation. Greenbank and Holm (*Ind. Eng. Chem.*, 1924, 16, 598) found that when air was led through butterfat in three bottles in succession, rancidity developed first in bottle No. 3 and last in bottle No. 1. This was ascribed to the accelerating effect of the volatile products of oxidation. The more recent work by Roschen and Newton (*Oil & Soap*, 1937, 14, 17) does not agree with their observation.

In this paper the effect of addition of small quantities of an oxidised sample of butterfat to a fresh fat, as also the effect of passing the volatile products of an oxidised sample through a fresh sample have been studied. In experiments 1 and 2 (Table I) respectively 1 and 5% of a rancid butterfat, whose peroxide value was 50, were added to a freshly prepared fat which showed no peroxide value.

To study the effect of volatile products of oxidation on the development of rancidity, a slow stream of nitrogen from a cylinder, absolutely freed from oxygen by passage through alkaline pyrogallol, was passed for 8 hours through a sample of highly rancid fat (P.V. 50), kept over a boiling water-bath, and the evolved gases, necessarily carrying the volatile products of oxidation (giving strongly aldehydic reaction), were then passed through a series of three conical flasks containing fresh butterfat

kept in a molten state in a bath at 40°. After the experiments, the contents of the different flasks were mixed together and stored at 37°, keeping the necessary control. Another experiment was performed to study the effect of the residual fat (rancid) obtained after the volatile aldehydes were removed by the nitrogen stream. The results are shown in Table I.

TABLE I

Effect of addition of peroxides and volatile products of oxidation on the development of rancidity of butterfat.

Description.	Kreis and peroxide value after							
	15 days		30 days		45 days		60 days	
	V. P.	K. V.	P. V.	K. V.	P. V.	K. V.	P. V.	K. V.
1. Butterfat +1% rancid fat (P. V. 50.0)	0.8	2.0	4.9	4.8	16.5	9.8	33.0	13.2
2. Butterfat +5% rancid fat (P. V. 50.0)	0.95	2.0	5.0	4.5	18.4	10.0	42.1	12.6
3. Butterfat + volatile products of oxidation	0.15	1.1	1.3	1.6	2.3	4.2	3.5	6.5
4. Butterfat %1 residue of oxidised fat from expt. (3)	0.85	2.1	5.0	5.0	15.8	10.0	35.5	13.0
5. Control	0.15	0.1	1.1	1.5	2.4	4.5	3.3	8.0

From experiments No. 1, 2 and 4, it can be confirmed that such products of oxidation as peroxides can reduce the induction period considerably, nearly to half its original value. Hence, it may be concluded that the active constituents of oxidised fat, viz. the reactive peroxides, are responsible for a large proportion of the pro-oxidant effect of the oxidised fats and for the apparently autocatalytic nature of the process of autoxidation and rancidity. On the other hand, the stability of the fresh fats towards oxidation is found to be practically unaffected by the volatile oxidation products, as evident from the peroxide and Kreis figure in Table I (cf. No. 3). Hence it may be concluded that the materials volatile at the boiling point of water which include the products responsible for rancid odour, are inactive as catalysts for the oxidation of butterfat.

Another group of strong chemical accelerators of oxidation are the metals. In view of their profound importance both from theoretical as also from industrial point of view they are dealt in a separate communication.